

Event-driven high-performance cloud computing for CRISPR-Cas9 guide RNA design

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I. INTRODUCTION

CRISPR-Cas9 has become the gold-standard technology for gene editing due to its simplicity and low cost. When a CRISPR-Cas9 nuclease is provided with a guide-RNA (gRNA), it can introduce a double-stranded DNA break at nearly any genomic loci of interest, giving the opportunity for that DNA site to be edited with great precision. It has truly modernised the gene editing toolset and has enabled large-scale and robust genomic studies. However, that has only been achieved through the design of high-quality gRNAs using high-performance computing.

There are two considerations when choosing a good-quality gRNA: (1) the efficiency of the gRNA, which relates to the edit being successful at the desired site, and (2) the specificity of the gRNA, which is a measure of a guide being unique to the desired site. A good quality gRNA is optimised such that both efficiency and specificity are maximised: when the desired site is targeted, it will certainly be edited, and it will be the one and only site edited.

We have optimised the selection of efficient gRNA by using a consensus-based method: we deem gRNA to be efficient when at least two of three independent methods agree [1]. That approach is more precise than any individual method alone and has resulted in our experiments seeing successful edits up to 99% of the time [2].

We have also carefully considered how the specificity of gRNA is evaluated. A naive approach would compare each gRNA to every CRISPR-targetable site on the genome. For large genomes, like plants and mammals, there can be hundreds of millions of CRISPR sites. That can incur trillions of sequence comparisons. We overcame this using a novel algorithm that reduces the number of wasted comparisons [3].

Our previously published method for designing good quality gRNA, named Crackling, is amongst the fastest tools available, and uses the most precise selection method, as described earlier [4]. It implements the consensus-based method with Python and leverages the performance of multithreading in C++ for evaluating the specificity of gRNA.

Crackling is fast and accurate, but not always do end-users have the necessary resources to run the program, and they may not necessarily have the expertise to work with bioinformatics programs. In an effort to overcome that, we are turning to high-performance computing environments provided by Amazon Web Services so users can click-to-deploy the software in their own cloud environment. Specifically, we are leveraging the dynamic compute environments available in the suite of “serverless cloud computing” technologies.

Serverless cloud computing refers to a service model that abstracts the underlying compute system away from the

developer. Rather than the research effort involving configuring and spinning up compute clusters to run experiments, efforts are devoted to actual science: designing methods for selecting good quality gRNA. After having those methods in place as software programs, they can be provided to a cloud vendor to execute upon events occurring, such as, a scientist requesting gRNA for a particular gene of a specified species (e.g., HSF1 in *acropora millepora*, as we have [2]). When no analysis is running, the infrastructure scales down to zero, and therefore, incurs no idle cost, unlike traditional server-based architectures.

In this work, we demonstrate an adaptation of Crackling that uses the serverless cloud computing model. That has increased: accessibility to Crackling by removing the need for specialist hardware resources and software skills to run the standalone version; scalability of Crackling by leveraging the seemingly-infinite resources available in the cloud; and, data privacy by enabling end-users to bring the software to their data rather than their data being sent to the software.

To that end, we present Crackling-Cloud: the first serverless-cloud-based CRISPR gRNA design pipeline. Crackling-Cloud is publicly available on GitHub as open-source software under the terms of the BSD 3-clause licence: <https://github.com/bmds-lab/Crackling-AWS>

II. MOTIVATION / BENEFITS

gRNA design is computationally demanding

The design of gRNA is computationally challenging, as the task quickly becomes more expensive proportional to genome size. Many gRNA design tools are limited by this challenge and often cannot scale to large genomes [4]. They attempt to overcome that by using specialised hardware and compute resources such as on-premises HPC clusters, which may not be readily available to end-users of these tools. A cloud-based solution can be run from anywhere, anytime, provided the user has access to the internet. Cloud also offers highly scalable and available systems that overcome issues regarding limited resources posed by traditional on-premises infrastructure. That includes avoiding wait times in queues and having to share hardware resources. Crackling-Cloud takes advantage of the seemingly-infinite scale of the cloud.

Bioinformatic skillsets

gRNA design tools are needed by end-users that may not be equipped with the technical knowledge to install and run bioinformatic tools. For instance, some biologists. Crackling-Cloud simplifies the set-up process greatly. Users can quickly and easily deploy the application to their AWS environment using the AWS-native template which describes the needed infrastructure and how to install the software. The end-user requires only an AWS account (simply username, password and a credit card for any costs incurred, which are minimal).

Users are not required to configure or manage servers, unlike traditional cloud-based solutions. Once deployed, a web-interface is used to start analyses and obtain results.

Data privacy

While some gRNA design methods are obtained from source and are, therefore, difficult to install, some are offered as “web servers” (in bioinformatics, web servers broadly refer to a website running on a traditional server that provides an interface to a bioinformatic tool installed on the same machine). The gRNA design tools in that category require end users to upload and share data with a third-party – incurring data sovereignty concerns and organisational constraints. By having a cloud-native pipeline that is available as a template, users can deploy Crackling-Cloud in their own cloud environment. Furthermore, they can bring the software to their data, rather than sending their data to the software. They can, if so desired, implement their own user access management and security measures, on top of the ones we provide by default. This provides control over where and how their data is stored and shared, ensuring data privacy.

Serverless model

Traditional server-based architectures are useful for large and long-running tasks. If the average capacity across a cluster is kept to a maximum, the approach becomes economically sound. However, the reality is that in the research context, that is often not the case. Having servers sit idle for long periods is wasteful and costly. The serverless model defers the impact of that by releasing the resources to other customers of the cloud vendor, incurring no idle cost when there is no work to complete. Furthermore, the friction of software development is reduced as the developer no longer needs to provision and maintain server infrastructure. Crackling-Cloud uses the serverless model to reduce idle cost to nearly zero by scaling down when there is no gRNA to design.

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

Crackling-Cloud is an event-driven pipeline that leverages a flexible, serverless architecture. The architecture could be implemented using the technologies of most modern cloud vendors. We selected Amazon Web Services (AWS) based on their position as the leading vendor and their robust service offering. AWS provides cloud services to many of the largest companies in the world, and to many research and education institutions. To that end, this section describes the implementation of Crackling-Cloud.

The entry point to the pipeline is via a HTTP API served through Amazon API Gateway. Two endpoints are available: submit job and retrieve results. To submit a job, the end-user provides the sequence of the gene to target, and to measure gRNA specificity across the entire genome, they also provide a NCBI Genome identifier. Upon submitting a job, the analysis infrastructure spins up from zero. The volume of needed resources is determined by the number of gRNA to assess. In return, a job identifier (ID) is provided to the user.

Results are associated with the job ID and can be retrieved from the database by querying the second API endpoint. We use Amazon DynamoDB as the database: a NoSQL-style database. The end-user can progressively retrieve results through a web-based interface. Furthermore, the HTTP API enables an advanced user to retrieve results using their own method (e.g., a custom-built software script, their own graphical interface, Excel, etc.).

Upon a job being submitted via a HTTP request, a database record is created. The event of that record being created triggers further data preparation steps. Those steps are orchestrated by AWS Lambda and Amazon Simple Queue Service (SQS). Lambda is a serverless run-time environment: no provisioning of servers is required; AWS handles that in the background as needed. We only provide our code, and any needed dependencies not installed by AWS. SQS is a queuing service that triggers Lambda to automatically handle, process and scale tasks based on the queued workload.

The first Lambda *function* has the task of preparing supplementary data (e.g., indexes of large data). The source of primary data could be a public repository (e.g., the NCBI Genome database) or a private Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3) bucket. S3 is an extremely reliable storage system. We connect S3 directly to Lambda so that the data of the end-user never leaves their cloud environment.

After data has been prepared, Lambda functions later in the pipeline perform the analysis on that data. The gRNA design methods of the standalone Crackling software exist in these Lambda functions, and therefore, produce identical results to the original, standalone tool. The designed gRNA and the associated efficiency and specificity results are written to DynamoDB alongside the job ID.

IV. PERFORMANCE BENCHMARK

We measured the performance of Crackling-Cloud using the same datasets that the standalone edition of the software was tested against. The sequence of the *rrs* gene (16S ribosomal RNA; NCBI gene ID 2700429) was used for each test. Crackling-Cloud identified 260 candidate gRNAs in that gene, and determined which of those was good quality for *Xiphophorus couchianus* (GCF_001444195.1) in average run-time of 83 seconds, for *Panicum hallii* (GCF_002211085.1) in 118 seconds, and for *Parus major* (GCF_001522545.3) in 195 seconds. Each experiment was performed as a *warm* run, meaning the infrastructure had already been initialised and was standing by, ready for processing, before timing out and scaling back to zero. In contrast, a *cold* run would have involved additional overhead from launching the serverless architecture, resulting in longer execution times—a typical characteristic and side effect of the serverless cloud computing model. The duration of a cold start can vary from a few milliseconds to over a second.

V. CONCLUSION

Crackling-Cloud incorporates the enhanced gRNA design methods as implemented in the standalone tool. By using the serverless model and technologies of Amazon Web Services, end-users can deploy it in their own cloud environment, avoiding barriers of traditional HPC environments.

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